

A Case-Study of Seychelles' Slave Routes Through its Folktales

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Introduction

Though few studies have been done in this area, Seychelles' folklore is a rich source of the routes of the enslaved peoples who formed the population of the archipelago, and their descendants (Choppy, 2022). This folklore forms part of the oral history that represents the memory and identity of the Seychellois people. When Europeans transferred slaves from the Bantu regions of Eastern Africa, the Swahili coast, and Madagascar, to the plantation islands of the Southwest Indian Ocean, these slaves brought with them a rich intangible cultural heritage which had already undergone various enriching transformations from previous inter-cultural exchanges on the continent (Haring, 2005).

Being one of the most important tools of diasporic memories, the folktale genre is naturally a palimpsest of the cultural interchanges which have taken place throughout the history of the Southwest Indian Ocean, including the precolonial era. For example, Haring says that even before East African stories were transported to the plantation islands via slavery, they were enriched by interchanges between Austronesians and Bantus in Madagascar (Haring, 2003, p.20). Stories from the Swahili Civilization had also been enriched by interchanges with the Arab Civilization (Geider, 2007). All these, when evidenced in the folklore of the region, are the beacons of the area's slave routes.

In this article, the specific element of folklore focused on is the folktale. Christine Goldberg points out that folktales are to the analysts of culture, what dreams are to the psychoanalyst: 'As people tell stories, they express and explore their ideas about the world and their place in it' (Goldberg, 1986, p.163). Story-telling among the slave population was part of their nostalgic memory making, as the stories they told were from their original homelands. The eventual transformations of the characters and events in the stories also reflect the slaves' and their descendants' reactions to slavery and their attempts at resistance.

Following a brief background of Seychelles as an ex-slave and colonial society, the article discusses the Seychellois folktale in the context of oral markers of Seychelles' slave routes, in two parts. The first part traces the origins of the stories through fragments of original African languages that formed the substrates of Seychelles Creole, and also through tale-types, symbols and characters found on the mainland. The second part discusses the personification

of the slave as the subaltern, and the slave's resistance to his/her subaltern status through the character of the African trickster hero.

Through both the tracing of the characters and story-types of Seychelles' folktales to their African origins, and a discussion of identity formation in an ex-slave society, these story samples map out the history of enslavement, aspirations of freedom, and intricate Creole heritage of the people of Seychelles. It is a brief testimony to the memory of a people which has tended to be ignored, perhaps deliberately, but that can be recovered through an analysis of the folktale corpus.

Background

Seychellois culture is a complex fusion of many cultures, spanning three continents. The largest contributors, the African slaves and their descendants, themselves represent a complex knitting together of a large cross-section of the Bantu ethnic group that stretched from Malawi in Central Africa, to the Swahili Coast, down to Southern Africa and Madagascar. As has been mentioned already, this group also contains elements of the Swahili culture through the mixing of the Arab and Bantu civilisations, and the Afro-Malagasy culture, through the mixing of Austronesians and East Coast Africans (Haring, 2003, p.20). Once the slaves had settled in the archipelago, their already rich heritage was further complicated by the imposition of the dominant European culture. However, the ensuing Creole identity and folklore has many aspects of stigmatization because of its history of slavery, and because of the maintained superiority of the Old World over the New World.

From most accounts, the story of Seychelles begins with the arrival of Europeans in the region, with its 'discovery' being attributed to the Portuguese explorer Vasco da Gama (Scarr, 2000, p.3; Franda, 1982, p.7). However, most history books about the islands do mention the fact that Arab and Indian navigators might possibly have known about the archipelago well before Europeans arrived there (Scarr, 2000, pp.2-3; Shillington, 2009, pp.2-3). There is even a suggestion that the Indonesian migration from the Sulawesi islands to Madagascar in 200-300 BC might have passed through Seychelles – otherwise, the archipelago lay off the main trading routes, thus the reason for their later settlement than other islands in the region (Franda, 1982, p.6).

It was only in 1756 that the islands were annexed by the French Crown and named after the controller-general of finances for the French colonial government, Vicomte Jean Moreau de Séchelles (Singer and Langdon, 2008, p.36; Franda, 1982, pp.9-10). The first attempt of settlement, however, was in 1770, when Brayer du Barré sent fifteen white men, led by Commandant Antoine Gillot, ostensibly to attempt a spice garden as directed by the then

Intendant of Ile de France, Pierre Poivre. They were accompanied by seven black male slaves, one black woman, and five Indians, which presumably was the first workforce of the settlement (Scarr, 2000, p.8). This first attempt, which took place on St. Anne Island, failed, but by 1786, the mainland, Mahé, could boast a small community comprising eight white families and four free black families and their slaves (Scarr, 2000, p.11).

The slaves far outnumbered the free citizens at the time (Nicholls, 2018, p.73). However, for much of its history, Seychellois society has been made up of a minority of white landowners and a majority of black slaves or people of slave descent (Campling et al., 2011, p.8). The first free Asians only began to migrate to the islands in the 1850s and they were also a minority (Franda, 1982, p.18).

Slavery was ostensibly abolished in the region, in 1835; but finding it difficult to give up such a lucrative business, white proprietors of land or ships in the Mascarenes and Seychelles, sometimes aided by Arab slave traders, continued trafficking well into the 19th century (Scarr, 2000, pp.27-29; Nicholls, 2018, p.167; de Commarmond and Gillieaux, 2024, p.9). In fact, some recently published data (de Commarmond and Gillieaux, 2024) suggest that slave trafficking in the Indian Ocean could have continued into the first quarter of the twentieth century at least, though this has to be historically verified. However, it has been established that the span of Seychelles' outer islands, and its strategic position between Africa, Madagascar and the Mascarenes, facilitated illegal trafficking (Scarr, 2000; Nicholls, 2018). The liberated Africans who were dumped in Seychelles by the British Navy from the 1860s up to the mid-1870s (Scarr, 2000) are testimony to this.

Being, for the most part, landless, ex-slaves and their descendants were dependent on their ex-masters' copra, cinnamon and vanilla plantations, and found life hardly any better than during slavery. The situation was further complicated by the arrival of the liberated Africans. The landowners took the opportunity to exploit the new arrivals as a sort of indentured labour, leaving the ex-slaves with fewer options (Scarr, 2000, p.69). This set the tone for the creation of a black, or Creole underclass who, because of their majority numbers, had a significant impact on the emergence of the Seychelles Creole culture and folklore (Choppy, 2022). Being forced to function in an imposed, alien language, they manipulated this language and refashioned it according to their own codes and knowledge systems, and retold inherited stories or told new ones according to their lifestyles and aspirations. These stories are the unacknowledged historical records of Seychelles' slaves and their descendants.

Origins

In tracing the origins of the slaves who were transported to Seychelles, one need go no further than the polyglot linguistic reality of Seychellois society, which is reflected in its folktales, and its folklore in general. This folklore represents the history of the Indian Ocean region as much as that of the Seychelles archipelago. Central to this are the tradition-bearers who brought with them, from their original homelands, the prototypes or, sometimes, bits and pieces of their intangible heritage, which were often refashioned or recreated to suit the new linguistic and socio-cultural reality (Choppy, 2022, p.22). The pieces of evidence that point to the origins of the African folktales include not only some original vocabulary from the substrate languages of Seychelles Creole but also, as mentioned already, tale-types, characters and specific story-telling techniques.

According to historical records, most of the early settlers who came to Seychelles moved from Mauritius and Reunion with their slaves (Franda, 1982; Scarr, 2000; Nicholls, 2018). Therefore, Seychelles shares the same source of slaves as these two islands. The general areas from which the slaves came was mainly the East African coast, from the Cape of Good Hope to the Port of Suez, including Ethiopia and Egypt. Some also came from Guinea and the West African coast, as will later be illustrated by vocabulary extracted from the folktales. In those early days, some slaves also came from the Malabar Coast of India, and from east of the Cape Cormorin area (Teelock and Sheriff, 2016, p.27). The slaves who were brought in later, mainly through the illegal slave trade which continued after abolition, and those who were dumped by the British Navy in the 1860s, would have come directly from Madagascar and East Africa (Nicholls, 2018).

The substrate languages included in the lexicon of Seychellois Creole is a good indication of the specific tribes that were included. Baker (1993) lists the following languages: Kikongo, Yao, Shimaore, Kiswahili, Shona, Makua, Kikamba, Bemba, Makonde, Giriyama, Nyanja, Nyamwezi (hailing from the Bantu tribes of East Africa); and Wolof, Fon, Bamana, and Manding (from the Kwa and Senegambian language families of West Africa) (Baker, 1993, pp.142-150). Bollée (1993), in her etymological dictionary, also identifies vocabulary from the Malagasy language, which originates mainly from Austronesian sources due to the maritime migrations from the Malay/Indonesian region about 2000-1500 years ago. As the Malagasy genetic heritage is almost equally mixed between Austronesian and East African (Bantu, for example, Makua), one can expect that its folklore would manifest influences of both traditions (Hurles et al., 2005).

Some samples of African vocabulary in Seychellois folktales

Soungoula is the most well-known folktale character in Seychelles. Haring (2005) points out that the trickster Soungoula is recognized by the Seychellois people as part of their African heritage, and traces the origins of this character to the Nyanja people of Malawi (Haring, 2005, p.294). Incidentally, Soungoula has a Swahili version, spelt *sungura* (Choppy and Salomon, 2004). Baker (1993) also identifies *sungula* as a Yao word, meaning 'Hare' (Baker, 1993, p.145).

Kousoupa is another well-known character in the Seychellois trickster stories. The exact nature of this character is however, ambiguous, and even Baker describes him as an 'unidentified animal in folktales' in reference to the Seychellois repertoire. Nevertheless, in the same entry, *kuzupa* is given as the Makhuwa name for hyena (Baker, 1993, p.143).

Kalkalandye is an interesting example in that it is the focus of a folktale that reveals two different African language groups, the title being *Tizan Kalkalandye*. The adjective in the title describing the hero, *kalkalandye*, is of Bantu origins. According to Baker, it comes from Kikamba, *ikala kalakala*, meaning 'resemble', and in Yao, *ka* (he, she, it) *landa* (which also means 'resemble'). *Kalkalandye* in Creole means 'alike', in other words, 'resemble' (Baker, 1993, p.143). It is used most often to describe two or more people who have dressed in similar clothes. In *Tizan Kalkalandye*, his mother, who has promised him to Loulou (equivalent of the ogre), dresses him in a red loincloth and sends Loulou to get him, but the hero tears the cloth and shares it with his friends so that they are all dressed the same. Loulou then is unable to know which one is his target. In another episode, Tizan evades Loulou's attempts to eat him by exchanging places with his father. The narrator's description of Loulou's devouring of Tizan's father is: 'He said: "That's him!" He grabbed him, nyanm-nyanm!'. *Nyanm-nyanm* means 'to eat' in Creole. According to Baker, it comes from Wolof, and has the same meaning in that language (Baker, 1993, p.150).

Some other selected vocabulary from the Seychellois folktale repertoire is listed in the table below, reflecting the polyglot nature of Seychellois society:

Vocabulary	Substrate language	Meaning	Source
<i>kapatya</i>	Swahili – <i>pakača</i> (Bollée, 1993, p.354)	Traditional basket made of coconut leaves.	<i>Angi ek Kanmeleon</i> (The Eel and the Chameleon). <i>Kont ek Lezann Vol. 3.</i> (1992). Lenstiti Kreol, Lans-o-pen. pp.23-26.
<i>fatak</i>	Malagasy – <i>fatakana</i> (Bollée, 1993, p.123)	Tall grass used for making brooms.	<i>Bonm Pityon i Ganny Son Mark Arete</i> (Old Pityon is taught a lesson). Leon Bonnelame (2020). <i>Zistwar Misterye.</i> Au Cap: Lenstiti Kreol Sesel, pp.2-35.
<i>katyolo</i>	Swahili – <i>nčoro</i> (Baker, 1993, p. 143)	Small pirogue. <i>Ka</i> is a diminutive prefix in Swahili.	
<i>kaskavel</i>	Portuguese – <i>cascavel</i> (Bollée, 1993, p.199)	Medicinal plant from which the seeds are used to fabricate a musical instrument, or rattle.	
<i>tartar</i>	Possibly Makua – <i>othatha</i> (Bollée, 1993, p.418) or Malagasy – <i>farafara</i> (Bollée, 1993, p.122)	(i) Raised shelving for drying fish, (ii) makeshift bed. Rough shelving for storing food.	<i>Bonnonm Blez</i> (Old Man Blaise). <i>Kont ek Lezann Vol. 1.</i> (1990). Lenstiti Kreol, Lans-O-Pen, pp.111-118.
<i>kelkel</i>	Malagasy – <i>kellech</i> (Bollée, 1993, p.213)	Armpit	<i>En Riz Soungoula</i> (Soungoula’s Trick). Penda Choppy (ed.). (2013). <i>Zistwar Soungoula.</i> National Heritage Research Section, Culture Department, Ministry of Tourism and Culture, pp.6-11.

Some characteristics of African story-telling in Seychelles Creole narratives

Some very distinct African characteristics of story-telling in traditional Seychellois narrations include the techniques of beginning and ending a story, and the use of special effects such as song, dance and onomatopoeic words. The following examples are given as illustration.

The most common introduction to a story-telling session in Seychelles Creole is the calling out of the word *Sirondann!* The audience replies, *Zanbaget!* These two words originate from the Makua tribe in Mozambique, *Sirondann* being *cirandani*, meaning wordplay, and *Zanbaget* being *tcampeteke*, which is an agreement to participate in a riddle session (Carpooran, 2013, pp. 47-48). Research carried out by Lyndon Harries supports this, though he says that *tcampeteke* is a Yao word of which the meaning is unknown (Harries, 1971, p.379). As for ending the story, one of the most common methods used in Seychelles is that of the narrator putting him/herself in the story and claiming that he/she was given a punch or a kick that landed him/her before his/her audience (Haring, 2003, p.30). Here is an illustration from the story entitled *Kader*.

He took the potion given to him by the male Warbler and gave it to the king. The king drank the hell water. A few days later, he died. Kader got his kingdom. The queen was very happy and set up house with Kader.

*One day I went by and said: 'Hi there, Kader, you've got yourself a beautiful woman!'
Kader got mad, he gave me a kick and I landed here!*

(Diallo et al., 1983, p.80)

According to Haring, this method enables the narrator to create some sort of other dimension within which the story was suggested to be happening for real, with the narrator acting as mediator between that story world and the audience in the real world (Haring, 2003, p.30). This is also similar to the East African tendency to enhance the narrative through song and drama (Haring, 2007). The East African origins of some stories are evidenced by remnants of the original languages they were told in. For example, not only has the story called *Tizan, Zann ek Loulou* (Little John, Jane and Loulou) been linked to *The Hyena Bridegroom* in Werner's *Tales of the Bantu* (1933), but its use of a magic song to lift the basket that enables the hero to escape with his sister creates suspense and drama at the crucial moment: '*Toi zironmon / Toi menga menga zironmon!*' (You pumpkin/You *menga menga* pumpkin!) (Choppy, 2022, p.271). The precise language it comes from and its meaning is not known, as this word is not included in either Baker's work on African contributions to French Creoles (1993), or Bollée's Indian Ocean Etymological Dictionary of non-French Creole words (1993). The same suspense is created in the narrator's re-enactment of Sounougoula's song and dance when the trickster convinces his friend Monkey to answer to his call and response: 'Who ate Papa Tig's children?', sang Sounougoula. 'I did, I did, I did!', replied Monkey. To add insult to injury,

Soungoula had Monkey sing that he had used the skins to make *beleko-beleka*, which is a type of drum (Kriegel and Neumann-Holzschuh, 2007, p.8). This of course further enrages Papa Tig, which gives the narrator plenty of dramatic action to end the story on.

These provide a very small sample of the contribution of Seychelles' enslaved peoples and their descendants to the rich cultural heritage of the islands. Out of some 200 stories which have been compiled into a database (Choppy, 2022), 44 stories have been identified as of African origin, and another 47 are replications or adaptations of these stories, featuring mainly the trickster hero Soungoula. This makes a total of 91 stories. The remaining stories in the database number 64 which have been categorized as of European origin, 18 from Asia and the East, and 27 which have been classified as unknown origin. From the East African contributions, one character stands out – the trickster, Soungoula. This warrants a closer look at this prototype of the East African story in the Seychelles Creole heritage.

The Trickster Hare – A case-study

In describing the folktale in the Southwestern Indian Ocean islands, Haring says that the African trickster figure 'is central to the common stock of island traditions' (2002, p.185). In *Stars and Keys* (2007), he backs this up by giving versions of the same trickster stories in Mauritius, Seychelles and Reunion. All of these stories also exist in Madagascar and the Comoros, since these islands, which are closest to the African mainland, experienced cultural interchange with the Bantu culture, and were later transferred to the Creole islands through slavery (Haring, 2005). Thus, one might say that the slaves from the Eastern African mainland and those from Madagascar or the Comoros, formed a kind of regional diaspora in Seychelles, because whatever other mixes they consisted of, they all had the Bantu tradition in common (Nicholls, 2018). Under the conditions of slavery and colonization, the trickster hero became a tool of subversion against their oppressors, and was also one of the few ways in which they could honour their cultural homeland.

The most well-known East African stories featuring the Trickster Hare, otherwise known as Soungoula, include the story of *Soungoula and the King's Pool*, which is a combination of *The Animals Dig a Well* (ATU 55) and *The Tarbaby and the Rabbit* (ATU 175); *The Race Between Soungoula and Tortoise* (ATU 275A); and *Soungoula at Tiger's Funeral* (no ATU classification), which is a 'Sham Dead' story. Most of these, along with others, are known not only in East Africa, but also in West Africa, and feature in the Creole stories of the Caribbean as well (Condé, 1978; Chamoiseau, 1988; Arnold, 1996).

The Metamorphosis of the Trickster Hare in a Creole society

In the introduction to one of the earliest compilations of Seychellois folktales and riddles featuring the trickster hero, the frequency of Sounougoula's appearance in Seychellois traditional narratives is remarked upon (Diallo, 1983, p.17). Sounougoula is generally known as a mythical personage, whose genetic origin is obscure. He is often described as half man, half animal, with pointed ears and a long tail. Both Choppy and Salomon (2004) and Diallo (1983) concur with this description. Because Sounougoula has always been associated with a tail, the tail has tended to be presumed as a long one. As such, most people have conceived Sounougoula as being a monkey. During a literary workshop at the Creole Institute in 2001, several people were asked to draw Sounougoula. Most people drew a monkey, with some drawing a man with long pointed ears and a long tail (Choppy and Salomon, 2004, p.4). This reveals the fact that the Seychellois people generally do not know the meaning of the word '*sounougoula*', which has been lost in the creolization process. However, the trickster hare existed before the word '*sounougoula*' entered the Creole lexicon.

Sounougoula seems to have metamorphosed from an earlier trickster known as Konper Lyev (Hare). According to Norbert Salomon, Konper Lyev was an adaptation of their original trickster by the African slaves of the first settlement, translated into Creole. Sounougoula came in the 1860s with the last waves of liberated Africans (Choppy and Salomon, 2004, p.1). There are several clues that suggest that this might be true. First, the earliest slaves who came with the French settlers from Mauritius and Reunion had already undergone a creolization process and were already creating a new folklore in their new language, Creole, by adapting the stories and characters from their old communities to the new environment (Haring, 2005). Baker and Corne have suggested that there was a significant component of West African slaves in the early creolization period of Mauritius (1982). Since these were likely to have been deliberately mixed with East African slaves, to avoid recreating new communities from the same areas, it would not be surprising that the name for the trickster hare would not be adopted from one of the original African languages, but rather adopted from the dominant French language at the time, thus *Compère Lièvre* or *Compère Lapin* (Chaudenson, 2001, pp.293-294).

Konper Lyev seems to have more or less phased out with the first few generations of settlers and their slaves. A member of the research team doing fieldwork on folklore in the 1980s, Mr. Marcel Rosalie, recalled the team collecting only one story featuring Konper Lyev instead of Sounougoula. This was a version of the race between two animals (ATU 275). However, this story is no longer available in the documentation section of the National Heritage Research and Protection Centre (Choppy and Salomon, 2004, pp.1-2). The fact that this character existed in Seychelles previously is confirmed by the Choppy and Salomon collection (2004) which contains five Konper Lyev stories. Only two of the stories in this compilation are interchangeable with Sounougoula stories: *Frer Zako i touy son manman* (The killing of mothers –

no ATU classification), and *Konper Lyev kot lanmor Papa Tig*, (Sham Dead, ATU 50A) which was confirmed by Marcel Rosalie (Choppy, 2022, pp.220-221). The other three stories seem to have more archaic plots and themes, which suggest that they are older than the Sounougoula stories. All three stories feature a wise protagonist who uses his wits to survive in a world where the odds are stacked against him, as a smaller and weaker animal. One story features Konper Lyev pitting his wits against the other animals to survive in the African jungle. In another, he is the hero in a creation story that tells how Tortoise got the cracks on his back. In the third one, we see an amalgamation of the East African trickster hero and the Malagasy malevolent spirit, Loulou. In this story, Hare cautions his wife against her wish to eat Loulou's eggs since, as he warns her, Loulou doesn't lay eggs. As she insists, he somehow finds the eggs in the roots of a baobab tree; she eats them, and dies before the next day (Choppy and Salomon, 2004). Sounougoula, on the other hand, though he does rely on his wits to survive, can also be both subaltern and a figure of resistance that is reflective of the slavery system.

Sounougoula's replacement of the French *Compère Lièvre*, is perhaps symptomatic of the resilience of Seychelles' enslaved peoples and their descendants. At any rate, the trickster's metamorphosis is part of the linguistic transformation of creolization which is associated with slavery. In both Konper Lyev and Sounougoula, we have some very valuable indicators of cultural and linguistic creolization in Seychelles (Choppy, 2022, p.222). Furthermore, Sounougoula's trajectory from subaltern to a figure of resistance in the Seychellois story repertoire, makes this character a representative of the African tradition bearers, who arose from the ashes of their previous cultures to build a new identity and a new culture.

An early version of the Tarbaby story

The Tarbaby story, *The Tarbaby and the Rabbit* (ATU 175), or *The Animals Dig a Well* (ATU 550) is probably the most well-known African trickster tale globally. Haring, and I concur with him, calls it 'Africa's best-known contribution to world culture' (2005, p.294). This is the episode where the trickster is either stuck on a Tarbaby or on Tortoise's back as punishment for stealing from the other animals or for refusing to dig a well, and inappropriately partaking of its water. It might be seen as a subversive story of power relationships and access to facilities that can fit in any society globally (Wagner, 2017). This story is also one of the most well-known in the Seychellois repertoire, and probably one of the oldest. This makes it part of the diasporic memory of the slaves and their descendants. In this section, we take a look at an early version of the story, in juxtaposition to similar versions on mainland Africa.

In Seychelles, *The Tarbaby and the Rabbit* (ATU 175), or *The Animals Dig a Well* (ATU 550) are commonly known as *Sounougoula and the King's Pool*. In the classical African version, all the animals collaborate to dig a well, with Hare refusing to help, but stealing the water for himself,

anyway, and spoiling it for others. Hare outwits all the bigger animals and overcomes them, until he is caught by Tortoise with birdlime on his shell (Haring, 2005, p.294). In the American version by Joel Chandler Harris, *The Wonderful Tarbaby Story* (1881), there is no mention of digging a well, but rather that Brer Fox was tired of being tricked by Brer Rabbit, and set up the Tarbaby to catch him. Being his usual arrogant self, Brer Rabbit got very angry when the Tarbaby refused to return his greeting and hit it, thus getting stuck. However, all of the African versions start with the need to extract water from the ground and Hare or Jackal, refusing to help (Ashliman, 2018).

This plot has been faithfully transferred to the Indian Ocean islands, inclusive of the honey that the trickster uses as bait to entice the guardians of the pool into letting him get the better of them. However, there is an interesting beginning to the story in some Seychellois versions, which does not appear in any of the African versions consulted online, though it appears in other Indian Ocean versions. The story starts with a consultation with God on how to deal with the drought, and only Tortoise was able to bring back God's message correctly (Haring, 2005, p.295).

In a Seychellois version, told by Mrs. Théophile Marie Rosalie, during a terrible drought the animals had a consultation and decided to go to God to ask where water could be found. Everybody who went forgot the correct answer, except for the last character, who was able to bring back the message correctly. Water was to be found by one of Africa's most precious trees, the ebony tree, referred to by the narrator as *Dibwa Debenm*, in Seychelles Creole. Everyone dug for water, except Sounboula, so when the well was ready, he was forbidden access to it and all the animals took turns guarding it. Sounboula however, convinced the guardians that he possessed the medicine which prevented death. The narrator told her audience, with a conspiratory laugh, that this was nothing but honey. But it convinced the guardians to allow the trickster access to the pool, until Tortoise decided to intervene.

Tortoise, always the nemesis of the redoubtable Sounboula, requested to be painted with *blakin* (Creole translation for 'blacking', another name for tar). So Sounboula was stuck, and was taken to the king for judgement. Sounboula convinced the king to have him tied up in banana cords and left in the hot afternoon sun. The informant ended the story here, being perhaps, the type of narrator who expected her audience to figure out the final ending for themselves, or because she expected everybody to know the ending anyway. The weakening and crackling of the weak banana cords in the hot sun is also a faithful rendition of classical versions from mainland Africa, as is testified by William Ernest Taylor's rendition of the story in his *Giryama Vocabulary and Collections* (nd).

This story was collected in 1980 by Marcel Rosalie, Gabriel Essack, and Abdourahamane Diallo. It was transcribed in 1985 by Marcel Rosalie. At the time of its collection, the

informant was already 82 years old. She might have forgotten which character came back from God with the correct information about where to find water because of her age, or the story might have been eroded because it is one of the oldest tale types circulated among the Eastern African diaspora. At any rate, the informant herself admits to having forgotten who was the successful message bearer: ‘*Tou sa ki ale pa kapab dir kot delo i ete. Dernye i ale. Mon’ n bliye non. I ale. Ler i vini i resi.*’ (Everybody that went could not tell where the water was. The last one went. I forget the name. He went. When he came back, he succeeded).

Mrs. Rosalie’s version identifies the tree that marked the hidden water as the ebony tree, a tree very much associated with mainland Africa. Though Seychelles has an abundance of hardwoods that are also found on the African mainland, the ebony tree does not exist in the islands. In folklore, it is a tree of memory that symbolizes *Grannter*, or the African homeland. With time, and with continuous creolization, these memories fade or gain new significance. For example, by 1980, Mrs. Rosalie’s version of the digging of the well does not identify the black substance that is used on Tortoise’s back to catch Soungoula as a kind of bee glue, but rather as *blakin*, a word which probably came into circulation fairly late into the British colonial period, and signifies the industrial era. In a Hottentot version (Bain, 1879) and another South African version (Honey, 1910), the black substance is identified as a kind of glue or wax found in bee-hives, whilst Haring identifies it as birdlime (2005).

The gradual erosion of certain physical details of the Tarbaby story that link it to the African mainland, need not be seen as a sort of distortion that renders the story less authentic. Rather, in Soungoula’s case, the changes become necessary because they symbolize the adaptation of the slave descendants who told these stories, to the socio-political and physical realities of their new environment. As Haring put it: ‘Where societies come into a colonized, multiracial existence for the benefit of a European minority, the normal reaction of the constituent groups is to renegotiate culture’ (2003, p.19). The evolution of Soungoula in the Seychellois repertoire of trickster stories, reflect his transformation from the traditional African trickster into the subaltern and figure of resistance that is symptomatic of a slave society. This transformation symbolizes both society’s rejection of the slave figure, and the slaves’ mockery of authority.

From subaltern to a figure of resistance

The trickster figure in Creole folktales is often a testimony of the slave mentality in both negative and positive ways. For example, in his analysis of Condé’s *La Civilisation du Bossale* (1978), A.J. Arnold discusses an important aspect of the Creole folktale, which is, that the slaves manifest both a moral and psychological interiorization of the master’s view of them (1996, p.263). Juxtaposing Glissant’s *Caribbean Discourse* (1989) with Condé’s work, he comes to the same conclusion as Glissant, that ‘the Creole folktale has verified the nature of the [plantation] system and its structure’ (Arnold, 1989, p.131). This interiorization is

characterized by the slaves' incorporation and expression of others' stereotypes of them through the animal characters which 'constituted the very face and expression of the culture of slavery' (Arnold, 1989, p.259). However, when put into context, there is an emerging pattern of survival and resistance throughout the stories. Arnold points out that, of the ten tales analysed by Condé, seven of these 'turn on the value of trickery for survival under conditions of extreme penury' (1996, pp.257-258). These tales not only represent the slaves' own exteriorization of the master's view of them, but also their own view of the master. For example, in the Caribbean context, Condé sees the slaves' representation of 'Massa' in the figure of Zamba (Hyena), who is regularly punished for his greed and cruelty in the African context. Seemingly a powerful figure, 'Massa' is portrayed as gullible and is easily fooled by the wily slave (Arnold, 1996, pp.258-259).

Similarly, trickster tales in Seychelles and the Mascarenes are celebrations of wit and 'the superiority of mind over brute force, denounce the abuse of power and affirm cleverness over pride and stupidity' (Haring, 2002, p.186). Our trickster hero, Soungoula, though he is often reviled by the rest of society for his undesirable habits, is just as often a tool with which the story-teller puts all forms of authority in their places, through subversion of power.

Slaves and subalterns

The stories of the Southwest Indian Ocean islands are described in terms of voiceless subalterns, due to their under-representation in literary discourse and their marginalization through postcolonial impediments (Haring, 2005; Boswell, 2017). This subalternization is emphasized in the figure of Soungoula. In several stories, he is a figure of ridicule, his aspirations are laughed at, as is his perpetual poverty, which causes him to resort to stealing, further deepening the general disdain against his character. Some extracts from the locally-created stories of the trickster, have been used to illustrate the trickster's subaltern status.

In *Gribouy Mistigri*, Soungoula's identity is ridiculed through a word-play around his name. The story is a new creation by renowned story-teller, Samuel Accouche, which was aired on Radio Seychelles in the 1980s, and published by the Creole Institute in its first volume of *Tales and Legends* (Payet, 1990, pp.33-45). From the beginning of the story, Soungoula is ridiculed through his name, 'Gribouy Mistigri'. In Seychelles Creole, *gribouy* refers to illegible scribbles. It suggests a poor attempt to make sense through writing. *Mistigri* is unknown. It is a made-up surname that is representative of the kind of caricatured constructions the Seychellois make of people they don't like, or don't know (Choppy, 2022, p.387). The irony is further deepened when Soungoula changes his name to Greyboy Mr. Grey to fool a hotel manager into taking him for a rich Canadian tourist. It manifests the narrator's vacillation between berating the trickster's aspiration to the tourist class, and showing up his poor knowledge of English surnames.

The negative emphasis put on Sougoula's tail in many of the new trickster stories is symbolic of his assumed bestiality and difference. Consequently, his tail, which disqualifies him from being human and, therefore, unworthy of consideration, is a great source of shame, and in all his cockiness, he is obliged to keep it hidden. In many stories, when it is discovered that he has a tail, he is sent packing. For example, in *Sougoula and Princess Liana*, he borrows Kousoupa's wedding jacket to court the princess, but instead of being received as a marriage prospect, he is given a good beating because his tail popped out of the usual hole in his pants.

In *Mr. François Poncé*, after impersonating a *blan deor* (white man from abroad), the sight of his tail sends the king mad with fury, especially since the usurper had spent the night dancing with the princess, and courting her, with the king's encouragement. *Mr. François Poncé* allows the reader to finally understand who Sougoula really is:

'Miss, but last night you danced with a monster.' The princess came to see. When she saw Sougoula, she ran to tell her father. When he saw all that wax melting down Sougoula's face, and all his straight hair stuck to the ground, with only some little grains of peppercorn left on his head, he was really angry.

This description of Sougoula is the stereotypical portrait of the African slave or people of African descent, in the extremely racialized societies of ex-slave milieux. The disgust and mistrust felt by those who consider themselves to be above this class of person is very obvious in this extract. The perceived higher classes are of course represented by the king and his entourage.

The shame built around Sougoula's tail, the contempt of his poverty, the emphasis on his being a thief, and his aspirations to being rich and being of consequence, which are all ridiculed, are, in effect, illustrative of A.J. Arnold's discussion of the slaves' moral and psychological interiorization of the master's view of them in *Creole stories* (1996, p.26). If indeed Sougoula is being compared to the slave, it means that the initial categorization of Africans as non-human as an excuse to enslave them during the Triangular Trade, has affected perceptions of this race seemingly permanently. This is the social stigma attached to Creoles, that dates back to slavery, and that is reflected in Creole folklore.

A figure of resistance

Language is one of the most important means by which Creole tales subvert power. Concurrently, it is seen as perhaps the most developed theme in Creole folktales (Seifert, 2002, p.222). The slaves were obliged to manage the situation, by overcoming the suppression of their own languages whilst existing in a multiplicity of knowledge systems, including folklore.

Haring proposes that ‘they developed a multi-voiced, deliberately ambiguous way of speaking’, so that the ambiguity of the trickster figure ‘became a guide for their real-life behaviour, especially for coping with authorities who were plainly bigger than they’ (2002, p.185). Soungoula is a master of the ambiguity of language and the power of double-entre. He manifests the slave descendants’ desire to ‘talk back’ to their oppressors as a form of resistance. Other forms of resistance employed by Soungoula include impersonation and duping. Some examples are given here.

In *Gribouy Mistigri*, in spite of the narrator’s emphasis on the immoral and ridiculous aspects of Soungoula, he ends up the winner. If, on the one hand, the trickster is seen as inappropriately ambitious by wishing to enjoy a few days in a hotel, he however achieves his aim by no other means than by duping two serious figures of authority. The first is the owner of a plantation, Mr. Mardigra, the very epitome of power in a plantation society. Soungoula, in this case described as a bow-legged little man who poses as an experienced fisherman, sells an imaginary property to Mardigra, who is eager to be taken fishing by the little man. He uses the money to fulfil his desire of staying in a hotel. Here, the trickster turns the tables on the rich proprietor by taking advantage of a couple of obvious weaknesses perceived in the white ruling class – that they could never get enough of buying properties, and that they liked to be taken for leisure activities such as fishing by dependant subalterns. Mr. Mardigra’s name is also a twist of humour in that it makes a mockery of the landowner’s sense of taste. The second person of authority to be duped in this story is of course the hotel manager, who believes Soungoula’s story of being a rich Canadian businessman, just because the guy could speak a few words of English.

In *Mr. François Poncé*, though he is revealed as the little black bête with peppercorn hair and a tail at the end of the ball, as he reminds the king, ‘*Mon Rwa, ou pa kapab koz mwan mirak, mon’n dans avek ou fanm, mon’n anbras ou fiy, ki ou kapab dir mwan?*’ (Your Majesty, you cannot be sarcastic with me, I danced with your wife, I kissed your daughter. What can you say to me?). This is the epitome of the subaltern resisting from below, of the subversion of power by the underdog, through storytelling, which is symptomatic of Creole trickster tales, born out of slavery and the plantation system (Chamoiseau, 1994, p.xii; Haring, 2002, pp.185-186; Seifert, 2002, p.218).

In both stories, Soungoula uses impersonation to achieve his ends. This worked because the system allowed for a person who was white, and who was rich, to be given precedence in any situation. So Soungoula’s declaration that he was a Canadian businessman was sufficient to gain him entry to the hotel, plus he had the money he had tricked Mr. Mardigra into paying him. Thus, for once, money talked for the underdog. He also gained entry to the king’s ball in *Mr. François Poncé* because he seemed like a distinguished white man – and again, he impersonated a white foreigner. His audacity in dancing with the king’s wife and kissing his

daughter during the ball is also symbolic of the belief in slave societies and Creole societies, that the slave craved physical intimacy with white people. For Sounougoula, it was most likely a show of his ability to be part of their otherwise, inaccessible society.

Conclusion

Though Sounougoula is a well-known folktale character in Seychelles, few Seychellois have associated his character and other animal characters in the local folktale repertoire with slavery (Choppy, 2022). In fact, there is a paucity of publications on the slavery period in Seychelles and the lasting impact it has had on the Seychellois society (Neumann, 1980; Choppy, 2022). Few history books that exist on Seychelles have paid attention to the origins of the slaves, the routes they were taken through, and their contributions to the rich tapestry of Seychelles' intangible cultural heritage. History books, and other archived documents in written form, also tend to be official records, and since slaves and their descendants were very rarely in such official positions as to enable them to give an account of events from their own viewpoints, oral history handed down through folklore can be considered as more representative of their viewpoints (Choppy, 2022).

The choice of folktales as a corpus for this study was prompted by the fact that they are particularly rich in data and can represent not only socio-cultural but also historical phenomena. This genre is also a very important aspect of intangible cultural heritage, especially in the context of the enslaved peoples and their descendants who were brought to this archipelago to provide labour, but who ended up playing a major role in the identity formations of this society. In their journey from the African mainland to the islands, they followed not only the routes of slavery, but journeyed from subalterns to figures of resistance. This resistance is manifested in the constant power-play between the underdog and the master in the folktales, which in their turn, reflect the complexities of a society once built on the domination of one race over another, but now considered by some as a melting-pot, a classless society (Bueger and Wivel, 2018).

References

- Arnold, A.J. (1996). *Monsters, Tricksters and Sacred Cows: Animal Tales and American Identities*, Charlottesville, VA: University Press of Virginia.
- Ashliman, D.L. (2018). *Folktales of Aarne-Thompson-Uther Types 175 and 1310A*. Retrieved from: <https://sites.pitt.edu/~dash/type0175.html#harris>
- Bain, T. (1879). *Folk-Lore Journal* [of South Africa], 1 (4), pp.69-73. Retrieved from: <https://sites.pitt.edu/~dash/type0175.html#bain>

- Baker P., (1993). 'Assessing the African Contribution to French-Based Creoles.' In Salikoko S. Mufwene (ed.). *Africanisms in Afro-American Language Varieties*, pp.123-155. Athens, Georgia: University of Georgia Press.
- Baker, P. and Corne, C. (1982). *Isle de France Creole: Affinities and Origins*. Ann Arbor: Karoma Publishers.
- Bollée, A. (1993). *Dictionnaire étymologique des créoles français de l'Océan Indien*. Hamburg: Helmut Buske Verlag.
- Boswell, R. (2017) 'Sensuous stories in the Indian Ocean Islands'. *The Senses and Society: The Senses and Urban Public Space*, 12 (2), pp.193-208. Retrieved from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17458927.2017.1319603>
- Bueger, C. and Wivel, A. (2018). 'How do small states maximize influence? Creole diplomacy and the smart state foreign policy of the Seychelles'. *Journal of the Indian Ocean Region*, 14 (2), pp.170-188.
- Campling, L., Confiance, H. and Purvis, M.T. (2011). *Social Policies in Seychelles*. London: Commonwealth Secretariat.
- Carpooran, A. (2013). *Proverb ek Sirandann Repiblik Moris*, Mauritius: Ministry of Arts and Culture.
- Chamoiseau, P. (1988). *Au temps de l'antan: Contes du pays Martinique: Fées et Gestes*. Paris: Hatier.
- Chaudenson, R. (2001). *Creolization of Language and Culture*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Choppy, P. and Salomon, N. (2004). *Soungoula ek Bann Konper*, Au Cap, Seychelles: Creole Institute.
- Choppy, T.P. (2022). 'Creativity, Creolization and Identity in Seychellois Creole Folktales'. PhD thesis, University of Malta. Retrieved from: https://www.um.edu.mt/library/oar/bitstream/123456789/111109/1/2301ISSISS600005069745_1.PDF
- Condé, M. (1978). *La civilisation du bossale: réflexions sur la littérature orale de la Guadeloupe et de la Martinique*. Paris: L'Harmattan.
- De Commarmond, O. and Gillieaux, C. (2024). *Memories of Slavery: Oral accounts of the vestiges of slavery in Seychelles*. Edited by Theresia Penda Choppy and Cindy Moka. Seychelles: UniSey Press.
- Diallo, A., Rosalie, M., Essack, G. and Labiche, E. (1983). *Contes, Devinettes et Jeux de Mots des Seychelles*, Paris : Editions Akpagnon.
- Franda, M. (1982). *The Seychelles: Unquiet Islands*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
- Geider, T. (2007). 'Alfu Lela Ulela: The Thousand and One Nights in Swahili-speaking East Africa' In Ulrich Marzolph (ed.). *The Arabian Nights in Transnational Perspective*, pp.183-200. Detroit, MI: Wayne State University Press.
- Glissant, É. and Dash, J.M. (1989). *Caribbean Discourse: Selected essays*. Charlottesville, VA: University Press of Virginia.
- Goldberg, C. (1986). 'The Construction of Folktales', *Journal of Folklore Research*, 23 (2/3), pp.163-176, Special Double Issue: The Comparative Method in Folklore. Indiana: Indiana University Press. Retrieved from: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3814446>
- Haring, L. (2002). 'African Folktales and Creolization in the Indian Ocean Islands'. *Research in African Literatures*, 33 (3), pp.182-199. Retrieved from: <http://www.jstor.com/stable/3820689>

- Haring, L. (2003). 'Techniques of Creolization'. *The Journal of American Folklore*, 116 (459), pp.19-3. Retrieved from: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4137940>
- Haring, L. (2005). 'Eastward to the Islands: The Other Diaspora'. *The Journal of American Folklore*, 118 (469), pp.290-307. Retrieved from: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4137915>
- Haring, L. (2007). *Stars and Keys: Folktales and Creolization in the Indian Ocean*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- Harries, L. (1971). 'The Riddle in Africa'. *Journal of American Folklore*, 84 (334),pp. 377-393.
- Harris, J.C. (1881). *Uncle Remus: His Songs and His Sayings. The Folk-Lore of the Old Plantation*. New York: D. Appleton and Company, Retrieved from: <https://sites.pitt.edu/~dash/type0175.html#edwards>
- Honey, J.A. (1910). *South-African Folk-Tales*. New York: The Baker & Taylor Company. Retrieved from: <https://sites.pitt.edu/~dash/type0175.html#bain>
- Hurles, M.E., Sykes, B.C., Jobling, M A. and Forster, P. (2005). 'The Dual Origin of the Malagasy in Island Southeast Asia and East Africa: Evidence from Maternal and Paternal Lineages'. *The American Journal of Human Genetics, American Society of Human Genetics*, 76 (5),pp. 894–901. Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1199379/>
- Kriegel, S. and Neumann-Holzschuh, I. (eds.) (2007). 'Sirandann ! Zanbaget ! Contes créoles des Seychelles'. *Creolica*, mardi 26 juin 2007. Regensburg, Germany: Universität Regensburg, Collectés par A. Bollée et I. Neumann-Holzschuh. Retrieved from: <https://www.creolica.net/article-61.html>
- Neumann, I. (1980). 'Les Contes Créoles Seychellois'. *Études Créoles*, 2 (01-12), pp.41-53. Ottawa: AUPELF.
- Nicholls, P.A. (2018). *The Door to the Coast of Africa: Seychelles in the Mascarene Slave Trade, 1770–1830*. PhD Thesis, University of Kent. <https://kar.kent.ac.uk/67029>
- Payet, F. (ed.) (1990). *Kont ek Lezann Seselwa Volim I*. Lans-o-pen, Seychelles: Lenstiti Kreol.
- Scarr, D. (2000). *Seychelles since 1770: History of a Slave and Post-Slavery Society*. London: Hurst and Company.
- Seifert, L.C. (2002). 'Orality, History, and "Creoleness" in Patrick Chamoiseau's *Creole Folktales*'. In *Marvels & Tales*, 16 (2), pp.214-230.
- Shillington, K. (2009). *History of Modern Seychelles*. Oxford: Macmillan Publishers Limited.
- Singer, B. and Langdon, J. (2008). *Cultured Force: Makers and Defenders of the French Colonial Empire*, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Taylor, W.E. (nd). 'Giryama Vocabulary and Collections'. *Sacred Texts, Africa*. Retrieved from: <https://www.sacred-texts.com/afr/mlb/mlb19.htm>
- Teelock, V. and Sheriff, A. (2016). 'Slavery and the Slave Trade in the Indian Ocean'. In Abdul Sheriff, Vijayalakshmi Teelock, Saada Omar Wahab and Satyendra Peerthum (eds.), *Transition from Slavery in Zanzibar and Mauritius: A Comparative History*, pp.25-43, Dakar: CODESRIA. Retrieved from: <https://www.publication.codesria.org/index.php/pub/catalog/download/37/121/283?inline=1>
- Wagner, B. (2017). *The Tar Baby: A Global History*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.23943/princeton/9780691172637.001.0001>

Werner A. (1933). *Myths and Legends of the Bantu*. London: George G. Harrap & Co. Ltd. Retrieved from: Sacred Texts: Africa, <https://www.sacredtexts.com/afr/mlb/mlb15.htm>

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